

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. *This article highlights the role of modern pedagogical approaches in fostering and developing interest in foreign languages, particularly English, among primary school students. It analyzes the importance of using innovative methods in English language teaching and evaluates their effectiveness in enhancing students' language skills.*

Keywords: *primary education, innovative method, interactive games, visual aids, sensory-based learning, multimedia resources.*

Recently, the number of people of all ages who are learning English has been increasing significantly. The reason for this is that it is becoming increasingly difficult to live without knowing English in the process of life. However, language learning also depends on the age.

Scientists have even proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults.

The natural tendency of children to learn languages, their strong imitation ability, the fact that children have more time than adults, and the ability to quickly memorize the information they have learned are some of the main reasons for this.

In today's era of globalization, it is becoming necessary for every person to know a foreign language. From this point of view, it has become an urgent issue to start the process of teaching foreign languages as early as possible - from the primary education stage.

The organization of teaching English in primary grades based on innovative and interesting methods was brought to a new level by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" No. PQ-1875 dated December 10, 2012. In accordance with this document, English began to be taught from the 1st grade, and this process was enriched with various visual aids, games and interactive methods.

Research shows that young children, namely primary school students, have high abilities in learning languages. This is due to their ability to imitate, remember and quickly form speech.

For example, the Japanese author Masaru Ibuka, in his famous work "It's Too Late After

Three", emphasizes the potential for language learning in childhood as follows: "A child's brain is capable of absorbing an unlimited amount of information."

It is advisable for teachers to use innovative methods to arouse and strengthen interest in language among primary school students. Some of these methods are analyzed below:

1. Visual memorization.

Since visual memory in young children is stronger than auditory memory, the use of pictures, posters, realia, and other visual aids in the lesson is effective. For example, by showing words such as "book," "pen," and "window" together with appropriate objects, children's vocabulary naturally increases.

2. Mixed methods

The combination of several methods increases students' interest in the lesson. In this case, the use of singing, drawing, movement games, and pantomime elements enlivens the teaching process and ensures the activity of students with different levels of intelligence.

3. Learning through cartoons

Watching English cartoons is not only an interesting but also a memorable educational resource for students. Contextual words are learned through the actions, facial expressions, and expressions of cartoon characters.

4. Learning the language through fun games

Games arouse the desire to compete in children, develop competencies such as concentration, quick thinking, and memorization. Classic games such as "Memory Game", "Simon says", "What's missing?" play an important role in organizing English lessons in a lively and interactive way.

5. Sensory-based learning

Conducting exercises through seeing, hearing, touching, tasting, and smelling helps to retain knowledge in the child's mind more deeply and for a long time. The opinions of psychologists also play an important role in the process of studying this method. In particular, it is emphasized that in order to increase the effectiveness of education in children, it is necessary to use as many sensory organs as possible at the same time.

The methods considered above show that the student's active participation in the language learning process, his interest in the lesson, and his desire for independent learning directly depend on the methods used. In particular, training with the participation of the senses is more effective than other methods.

In conclusion, the use of innovative, modern and actively engaging methods in teaching English in primary grades not only increases the interest of students, but also strengthens their passion for language learning and creates a solid foundation for the next stages. In this regard, the teacher is required to have pedagogical skills, openness to innovation and the ability to adapt modern technologies to the lesson.

References:

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